

ТЕХНИКА ФАНЛАРИ

7 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

ТОМ 7, НОМЕР 1

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

VOLUME 7, ISSUE 1

ТЕХНИКА ФАНЛАРИ

ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ | TECHNICAL SCIENCES

№1 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9696-2024-1>

Бош мухаррир:
Главный редактор:
Chief Editor:

Юсулбеков Нодирбек Рустамбекович
Техника-фанлари доктори, профессор

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Игамбердиев Хусан Закирович
Техника-фанлари доктори, профессор

TAHRIRIY MASLAHAT KENGASHI | EDITORIAL BOARD | РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

Мардонов Ботир - техника фанлари доктори, профессор, "Табий тоаларни дастлабки ишлаш технологияси" кафедра профессори.

Исматуллаев Патхулла Рахматович - Техника-фанлари доктори, профессор.

Рахмонов Анвар Тожибоевич - Техника-фанлари доктори, профессор

Хакимов Шеркул Шергозиевич - техника фанлари доктори, доцент, "Технологик машиналар ва жиҳозлар" кафедра доценти

Шин Илларион Георгиевич - техника фанлари доктори, доцент, "Машинашунослик ва сервис хизмати" кафедра профессори

Джураев Анвар - техника фанлари доктори, профессор, "Машинашунослик ва сервис хизмати" кафедра профессори

Хамраева Сановар Атоевна - техника фанлари доктори, профессор, Магистратура бўлими бошлиғи

Нигматова Фотима Усмановна - техника фанлари доктори, профессор, "Тикув буюмларини конструкциялаш ва технологияси" кафедра профессори

Ташпулатов Салих Шукурович - техника фанлари доктори, профессор, "Костюм дизайни" кафедра профессори

Набиева Ирода Абдусаматовна - техника фанлари доктори, профессор, "Кимёвий технология" кафедраси мудири

Худайбердиева Дильфуза Бахрамовна - техника фанлари доктори, профессор, "Кимёвий технология" кафедраси профессори

Бабаханова Халима Абишевна - техника фанлари доктори, доцент, "Матбаа ва қадоклаш жараёнлари технологияси" кафедраси профессори

Рафиков Адхам Салимович - профессор, "Кимё" кафедраси мудири

Ахмедов Жаҳонгир Адхамович - техника фанлари доктори, доцент, "Ипак ва йиғириш технологияси" кафедра доценти

Юлдашев Уришбой - Техника фанлари доктори

Усманкулов Алишер Қодирқулович - Техника фанлари доктори

Абдуназаров Жамшид Нурмухаматович - Техника фанлари номзоди

Почужевский Олег Дмитриевич - кандидат технических наук, доцент по кафедре "Подъемно-транспортные машины", работаю доцентом кафедры "Автомобильный транспорт" Криворожского национального университета (Украина, г. Кривой Рог).

Полвонов Омонжон Хусанбой ўғли - Ислом Каримов номидаги Тошкент давлат техника университети Кўкон филиали ассистенти.

Тошпулатов Исломжон Адилжон ўғли - Ислом Каримов номидаги Тошкент давлат техника университети Кўкон филиали ассистенти

Page Maker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

МУНДАРИЖА | СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1. Usmanov Xayrulla, Pardaev Xonimkul, Safarov Miraziz PAXTA TOLASINI NAMLASH JARAYONIGA OID REGRESSIYA TENGLAMALARINI QURISH.....	4
2. R.K. Huseynov., S.P. Isganderova., Rustamova S.K., Yusubova L.E., Zarbaliyeva V.S., Nino Jonjoladze STUDY METHODOLOGY OF ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY IN SiS:Er MONOCRYSTAL.....	11
3. Ishniyazov Odil Olimovich FELLEGI-SUNTER METHOD FOR CONNECTING RECORDS.....	14
4. Chulliyev Shokhrukh Ibadullayevich, Ishniyazov Odil Olimovich TEXT-TO-VIDEO SYNTHESIS: BRIDGING LANGUAGE AND VISUALS THROUGH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE.....	19
5. Ishniyazov Odil Olimovich, Babajanov Mumin Rajabovich THE ROLE OF THE BLOCKING METHOD IN LINKING RECORDS.....	24

Ishniyazov Odil Olimovich

(Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi,
oishniyazov@gmail.com)

Babajanov Mumin Rajabovich

(PERFECT UNIVERSITY, mrbabajanov@gail.com)

THE ROLE OF THE BLOCKING METHOD IN LINKING RECORDS

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12103985>

ABSTRACT

The blocking method is an efficient search optimization technique used to expedite the process of querying and retrieving data from databases or tables. By organizing the data into blocks, each representing a subset of the database, this method facilitates pre-query filtering of relevant records. Users formulate search queries based on entered information, and the system navigates through blocks to quickly identify and extract pertinent data.

Keywords: Blocking method, Search optimization, Data retrieval, Querying, Databases, Block organization, Search queries, Information retrieval, Processor power, Disk writing time, Large databases, Information extraction, Data organization, Efficiency.

Ишниязов Одил Олимович

(Ташкентский университет информационных технологий имени Мухаммада аль-Хорезми, oishniyazov@gmail.com)

Бабаджанов Мумин Раджабович

(PERFECT UNIVERSITY, mrbabajanov@gail.com)

РОЛЬ МЕТОДА БЛОКИРОВКИ В СВЯЗЫВАНИИ ЗАПИСЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Метод блокировки - это эффективный метод поисковой оптимизации, используемый для ускорения процесса запроса и извлечения данных из баз данных или таблиц. Благодаря организации данных в блоки, каждый из которых представляет подмножество базы данных, этот метод облегчает предварительную фильтрацию соответствующих записей. Пользователи формулируют поисковые запросы на основе введенной информации, а система перемещается по блокам, чтобы быстро идентифицировать и извлекать соответствующие данные.

Ключевые слова: Метод блокировки, поисковая оптимизация, Извлечение данных, Запрос, Базы данных, Блочная организация, Поисковые запросы, Извлечение информации, Мощность процессора, Время записи на диск, Большие базы данных, Поисковые операции, Организация данных, Эффективность.

Ishniyazov Odil Olimovich(Muhammad Al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti,
oishniyazov@gmail.com)**Babajanov Mo‘min Rajabovich**

(PERFECT UNIVERSITY, mrbabajanov@gail.com)

YOZUVLARNI BOG‘LASHDA BLOKLASH USULINING ROLI**ANNOTATSIYA**

bloklash usuli-bu ma‘lumotlar bazalaridan yoki jadvallardan ma‘lumotlarni so‘rash va olish jarayonini tezlashtirish uchun ishlatiladigan qidiruvni optimallashtirishning samarali usuli. Ma‘lumotlarni har biri ma‘lumotlar bazasining bir qismini ifodalovchi bloklarga ajratish orqali ushbu usul tegishli yozuvlarni so‘rovdan oldin filtrlashni osonlashtiradi. Foydalanuvchilar kiritilgan ma‘lumotlar asosida qidiruv so‘rovlarini shakllantiradilar va tizim tegishli ma‘lumotlarni tezda aniqlash va chiqarib olish uchun bloklar bo‘ylab harakatlanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: blokirovka qilish usuli, qidiruvni optimallashtirish, ma‘lumotlarni qidirish, so‘rov o‘tkazish, ma‘lumotlar bazalari, blokni tashkil qilish, qidiruv so‘rovlari, ma‘lumot olish, protsessor quvvati, diskni yozish vaqti, katta ma‘lumotlar bazalari, qidiruv operatsiyalari, ma‘lumotlarni tashkil qilish, samaradorlik.

The blocking method is a shortened search technique used to identify rows or entries in tables or databases. In this method, the data is divided into blocks, and each block may have specific characteristics based on the rows and columns in tables or the features of a database.

The main purpose of the blocking method is to expedite the process of searching for entries in a database and optimize the search. This method is particularly beneficial for efficiently managing large databases and speeding up the retrieval of information.

The blocking method can be performed in the following steps:

1. Division into blocks: entries in a database are divided into blocks according to established criteria. For example, records in a database may be by name, age, address, position, or other characteristics.

2. Query creation: the user or application automatically creates a query to complete the blocking. Criteria for block identification (e.g. name, age, address) are entered in the survey.

3. Block identification: blocks are identified using a query, which consists of rows and columns in tables (tables) or a database.

4. Identifying linking entries by performing a search: entries within blocks, those corresponding to query criteria are identified. Linking records within blocks provide quick access to search acceleration and data in the database.

5. Return results: when connecting records are found inside blocks, they are returned to the user or application. These records are used according to the result, according to sorting, filtering or other purposes.

The blocking method is a method that is very useful in optimizing the process of creating search queries and obtaining answers. This method involves filtering the database or tables of linking records before searching. This speeds up data detection and tracking processes as well as allowing very efficient use of resources (e.g. processor power, disk write time).

The blocking method speeds up the search by dividing the entries in the database into blocks according to different characteristics. This method is very used when developing optimized queries of databases and finding data quickly.

In general, it is possible to associate with the following types of properties:

1. ID: usually a unique ID will be available for each entry. Based on this ID, numerical values are given. Blocking by ID can help you quickly identify a record.

2. Text or Name: records can be names or texts. Blocking by features of this type can help speed up text-based search for records.

3. Number or Score: if records can get average grades (score), then blocking by numbers will be very useful.

4. Date: can be the date of creation of records. Blocking by these types of features can help you find records that match a specific date.

5. Geographical information: blocking records by Address, City or state, blocking by other geographical features can be used.

6. Categories: records can be based on some category. Category-by-Category blocking can help identify entries belonging to a specified category.

However, depending on the effectiveness and application of the blocking, you should explain what features should largely depend on the data in your database. These characteristics will be related to the structure and purpose of the database.

1-block-scheme. Algorithm of blocking method.

This block-scheme of the algorithm is implemented step by step as follows:

1. Start: the beginning of the algorithm.
2. Data reading: reading data from a database or table.
3. Dividing into blocks: dividing the read data into blocks according to different characteristics (ID, Name, Score, etc).
4. Query creation: create a query to perform a search for a user or application. This includes the necessary information (e.g. ID=2 or Name="Ali") to identify the blocks being linked.
5. Finding blocks: finding blocks that are being linked using a query.
6. Combining blocks: combining found connecting blocks. In this case, it is possible to attach the necessary blocks based on the search terms entered by the user from the query.
7. Output of the result: the output of data in the combined blocks or their use for the purposes derived from them.
8. Algorithm completion: completion of algorithm work.

List of references:

- [1] N. Adly. Efficient record linkage using a double embedding scheme. In DMIN, pages 274–281, 2009.
- [2] F. Afrati, A. D. Sarma, D. Menestrina, A. Parameswaran, and J. Ullman. Fuzzy joins using mapreduce. In ICDE, pages 498–509, 2012.
- [3] A. N. Aizawa and K. Oyama. A fast linkage detection scheme for multi-source information integration. In WIRI, pages 30–39, 2005.
- [4] A. Allam, S. Skiadopoulos, and P. Kalnis. Improved suffix blocking for record linkage and entity resolution. DKE, 117:98–113, 2018.
- [5] Y. Altowim, D. V. Kalashnikov, and S. Mehrotra. Progressive approach to relational entity resolution. PVLDB, 7(11):999–1010, 2014.
- [6] Y. Altowim and S. Mehrotra. Parallel progressive approach to entity resolution using mapreduce. In ICDE, pages 909–920, 2017.
- [7] A. Arasu, V. Ganti, and R. Kaushik. Efficient exact set-similarity joins. In VLDB, pages 918–929, 2006.

ТЕХНИКА ФАНЛАРИ

7 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ
ТОМ 7, НОМЕР 1

TECHNICAL SCIENCES
VOLUME 7, ISSUE 1

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000